

HYBRID VERSION OF LINGUISTICS WITH THE HUMANITARIAN DISCIPLINES. THE PECULIARITIES OF ETHNOLINGUISTICS IN LINGUISTICS

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Abstract: This article explores the integration of ethnolinguistics within linguistics, specifically within the hybrid version that combines linguistics with the humanities. Ethnolinguistics is an interdisciplinary area of study that explores the relationship between language and culture. It dates back to the early 20th century, when linguists and anthropologists recognized the value of studying the relationship between language and culture. The German linguist Wilhelm von Humboldt is known for having provided a model for ethnolinguistics, based on his work on the relationship between language and thought and his focus on the study of language in a cultural context.

Keywords: ethnolinguistics, linguistics, linguistic world image, concept, value, phraseology, cultural ethnolinguistics, ethnic factors, linguistics, language and culture, mythological creativity, lexemes, diachronic ethnolinguistics, ceremonial names, history of spiritual culture.

Аннотация: В данной статье исследуется интеграция этнолингвистики в лингвистику, в частности в гибридную версию, объединяющую лингвистику с гуманитарными науками. Этнолингвистика – это междисциплинарная область исследования, которая исследует взаимосвязь между языком и культурой. Оно восходит к началу 20 века, когда лингвисты и антропологи осознали ценность изучения взаимосвязи языка и культуры. Немецкий лингвист Вильгельм фон Гумбольдт известен тем, что предоставил модель этнолингвистики, основанную на его работах по взаимосвязи между языком и мышлением и его сосредоточении на изучении языка в культурном контексте.

Ключевые слова: этнолингвистика, языкознание, языковая картина мира, концепт, значение, фразеология, культурная этнолингвистика, этнические факторы, языкознание, язык и культура, мифологическое творчество, лексемы, диахронная этнолингвистика, обрядовые имена, история духовной культуры.

Introduction:

To begin with, the scientific area of linguistics has increasingly recognized the usefulness of multidisciplinary methodologies. This article discusses how linguistics has fused with other humanitarian fields, with a focus on ethnolinguistics.

The study of ethnolinguistics in world linguistics, as well as the relationship of ethnolinguistics with ethnoculture and language are discussed in this article. Ethnolinguistics is an expression of the ethnic aspect of language and the linguistic characteristics of an ethnos, ethnolinguistic processes in internal and interethnic relations, the role of language in the formation and activities of ethnic communities, language and traditional culture, ethnic originality of thought, ethnolinguistic classification of world languages.

In the recent years, ethnolinguistic research in linguistics became more active. Aspects of language and culture interdependence have been resurrected in world linguistics as a model of folk mentality, spiritual culture, folklore, mythology, ethnolinguistics in folklore genres.

Ethnolinguistics emerged as a separate branch of science in the nineteenth and twentieth centuries, and it flourished in the 1970s in the United States. The impact of socio-cultural factors on language has been studied in world linguistics by scientists such as D.H. Heims, H. Hoyer, G.M. Hyonigswald. In Russia, the names of F.I. Buslaev, A.N. Afanasev, and A.A. Potebnya are associated with the study of the problem. The ethnic characteristics of an ethnos that has long lived in the same area are primarily reflected in its language, as well as its traditional culture, are both unique.

The study of language from an ethnolinguistic perspective allows us to consider the mental characteristics of language and people, language and folk culture, language and folk art, in short. Ethnolinguistics is a science that studies the relationship between ethnos and language in all of its diversity is one of the areas that the researcher looks into.

The ethnic characteristics of an ethnos who have lived in the same area for a long time are primarily reflected in its language and traditional culture. The study of language from an ethnolinguistic perspective allows for consideration of the mental characteristics shared by language and people, language and folk culture, language and folk art, in short, language and people. As a result, the lexical study of ethnolinguistic units is a popular topic in world linguistics.

M.A.Yeremina, who studied the "lexical-semantic field of" human attitude to labor "in Russian folk dialects" from an ethnolinguistic perspective, sees labor as

a means of shaping the human spiritual world, emphasizing the ethnolinguistic nature of her research. The work combines the lexemes expressing the Russian people's positive and negative attitudes toward labor into a semantic motivational field, and the motivational semantic field is analyzed as ethnocultural information informing about the life of the Russian people. "Words and phrases expressing funeral rites" ethnolinguistic research in Bashkir" by L.R. Suleymanova (you are missing a verb there, please, relook this sentence)

Literature Analysis and Methods:

The study of ethnolinguistics and its relationship to linguistic science has evolved significantly since the mid-20th century.

The ethnic characteristics of an ethnic group that has lived in the same territory for a long time are most visible in its language, as well as traditional culture. The language study from an ethnolinguistic perspective view allows one to consider the mental language and people's characteristics. Spirituality, language and culture, and language and people's art; in a nutshell, language and people.

As a result, lexical studies of ethnolinguistic units are widely studied in world linguistics; in this regard, L.I. Larina, M.A. Eremina, L.R. Suleymanova, Sh.S. Nekushoeva, F.Kh. Gilfanova, M.V. Kalinina, Yu.A. Krivoshapova, Yu.A. Kulpinov, O.A. Dorofeeva, O.V. Gaponova's research is noteworthy [4,7,8].

Larina L.I. "Ethnolinguistically studied the terminology of weddings in the Kursk oasis." The work examines the components of the terms used in the region's wedding ceremonies, identifying thematic groups, lexical-semantic and regional aspects. The semantic group terms were ethnolinguistically analyzed based on observations of over 200 wedding ceremonies in the Course area.

M.A. Yerimina, who studied the lexical-semantic field of "human attitude to labor" in Russian folk dialects from an ethnolinguistic standpoint, regards labor as a means of shaping man's spiritual world, emphasizing that this research is ethnolinguistic. In the work, the lexemes expressing the positive and negative attitudes of the Russian people toward labor are combined into a semantic-motivational field, and the motivational semantic field is analyzed as ethnocultural information about the Russian people's lives.

L.R. Suleymanova's "Words and phrases expressing funeral rites in the Bashkir language" ethnolinguistic study (incomplete sentence). For the first time in Bashkir linguistics, the work is significant because it is an ethnolinguistic study of words and phrases describing funeral rites. The author describes four types of funeral units:

1. The pre-death stage
2. Death stage
3. The funeral stage
4. Memorial ceremony stage; she classifies all ceremonial terminology into five lexicalthematic groups:
 - 1) the names of the ceremonies;
 - 2) the names of the ceremonial actions;
 - 3) the names of the ceremony's participants;
 - 4) the names of the venue; and
 - 5) the names of the objects used in the ceremony.

The names of funeral rites are studied in depth in the dissertation, which spans pre-Islamic and Islamic periods.

Sh.S. Nekushoyeva investigated the lexical and semantic characteristics of nominative units used to name residential and commercial buildings, traditional foods, traditional clothing, and headgear.

L.R. Suleymanova conducts an ethnolinguistic study of the words and phrases representing the funeral in the Bashkir language. She investigates the ethnographic, folkloristic, and mythological aspects of ceremonies and groups both semantically and etymologically. This study is significant in Bashkir linguistics because it is the first theoretical examination of words and phrases that describe the characteristics of a funeral. The scholar divides the terms of the ceremony into four stages:

- words and phrases denoting the period of death;
- words and phrases denoting death;
- words and phrases denoting the funeral;
- words and phrases expressing memory;

The stages include a full explanation of the ritual words and terms that ensure the level of purification of the corpse in the afterlife.

Material and methods:

N.I. Tolstoy defines the tasks, subject, object, ethnolinguistic methods in the social sciences, and the relationship with other sciences. The object of N.I.Tolstoy ethnolinguistics is language, collective consciousness, national mentality, forms and manifestations of the "world image" formed in a particular ethnos, that is, folk culture, in all its forms, oral vocabulary and phraseology, paremiology, folklore texts, various rituals, mental beliefs. The ethnic units that make up a culture's content are the focus of ethnolinguistics. He claims that the

goal of ethnolinguistics is to semantically reconstruct the traditional image of the world, its worldview, and value system.

In addition to this, N.I. Tolstoy defined each component of the word ethnolinguistics in his approach, which he called ethnolinguistics. The first section focuses on traditional ethnos, ethnic, regional, and dialectal forms, while the second section, linguistics, focuses on language as the primary source for studying traditional culture. Ethnolinguistics (Greek ethnos - people, tribe) is a branch of linguistics that studies the relationship between language and culture, as well as different ethnic groups' perceptions of the world. Ethnolinguistics (Ethnolinguistics; Ethnolinguistics, Anthropological linguistics; Ethnolinguistique) is a science that studies the relationship between ethnos and language in all of its diversity.

Ethnolinguistics research investigates relation between language and culture, especially how different cultural groups perceive, interpret, and put reality into words. This scientific field of study involves the branch of anthropology called ethnology, which investigates the social aspects of cultural groups, comparing and drawing distinctions between them; and linguistics, the scientific discipline that studies language – the systematic study of any language that focuses on its structure (e.g., units, rules that command the association of units). A variety of methods are used while investigating language and culture.

Qualitative and quantitative approaches, as well as mixed methods designs, are among these methods. Qualitative methods like ethnography and discourse analysis provide detailed insights into the social contexts of language use. Immersion in a community or group is used in ethnographic studies to better understand the sociocultural factors that influence language practices. Language constructs and reflects social identities, power relations, and ideologies, according to discourse analysis.

Discussion and results:

According to the findings of the scientific analysis, folk culture should be studied in ethnic, regional, and dialectal forms, and language is the primary source for studying national culture. Many researchers regard culture, like natural language, as a system of signs, a semiotic system, or a language in the semiotic sense. The dialectal forms of the Uzbek language and culture, particularly paremas, are radically different. It should also be noted that modern liberal arts education is distinguished by a shift to the anthropological (or anthropocentric) paradigm, which holds that culture and language are inextricably linked to the

human mind - its consciousness, thinking, subject-practical, and spiritual activity.

The research is carried out using ethnolinguistic analysis of language paremological units. The main source of this approach is an understanding of cultural integrity, i.e., ethnolinguistics, which perceives the semantic unity of all its forms and genres (language, ritual, belief, folk art, parema units) and creates human culture. Ethnolinguistics is a holistic approach to the study of ethnic culture, defined as "the study of language through the prism of human consciousness, mentality, daily and ceremonial movements, mythological ideas, and mythological creativity," or in another formulation by the same authors, "the study of language through the prism of human consciousness, mentality, daily and ceremonial movements, mythological ideas, and myth. This is achieved through the use of a "complex science to learn." Spiritual culture and its language (is it a phrase or a sentence?). Because there is a gap in the study of the language of traditional folk culture, ethnolinguistics is a very relevant subject in the professional training of specialists in ethnic culture of the people. According to diagnostic data, the majority of people do not know the origin of ethnic units in a language, all of the possibilities of language, and they lack sufficient knowledge of linguistic and cultural terminology. The observed results show that the required methodological literature (programs, textbooks, etc.) is not available - this is in the system of training specialists in the study of ethnic culture of the people and the creation of scientific innovation in this area is yet another demonstration of ethnolinguistics' importance.

Conclusion:

Ethnolinguistics is a relatively new science, and, as is often the case with new areas of humanitarian knowledge, the scope of its subject is not clearly defined, i.e., what elements of reality it studies remain amorphous. To begin, ethnolinguistics is an interdisciplinary science. Many such frontier areas of knowledge have emerged in recent decades, and the emergence of "sciences at the interface" is a defining feature of modern science, both humanities and natural sciences.

Ethnolinguistics is a subfield of linguistics that investigates the spiritual, cultural, and ethnic aspects of people's lives and how they manifest themselves in language. It appears that language not only reflects reality, but also interprets it and embodies the human life situation. As a result, the ethnolinguistic plan's study of language units is always relevant. The ethnic characteristics of an ethnos who have lived in the same area for a long time are primarily reflected in

its language and traditional culture. The study of language from an ethnolinguistic perspective allows for the examination of the mental characteristics shared by language and people, language and folk culture, language and folk art, in short, language and people. As a result, lexical studies of ethnolinguistic units are widely studied in world linguistics.

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